

GRAPHIC REPAIR OF HISTORICAL MONUMENTS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN OF THE XVIII-XIX CENTURIES, PRESERVED IN RUINS AND NOT PRESERVED, RESTORATION AND USE FOR TOURIST PURPOSES

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Annotation: The story of the "restoration" of architectural monuments in Karakalpakstan has gone into a nasty a cappella mode: each voice leads its own party, not really caring about agreeing with others. Recall how this episode appeared in the media. First, the journalist Evgenia Grande published a material [1], which spoke about the unusual "restoration" of historical monuments of Karakalpakia: under the pretext of their dilapidation, the monuments were updated beyond recognition, or rather, they were built anew, and in modern materials and fantasy forms.

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Then the regional department of the Ministry of Culture stated that the demolition of the mausoleum of Shamunabi (Shamun-nabi, Shamun-nabi - ed.) in the suburbs of Nukus was a forced measure. Allegedly, the restoration work organized at the NPU for the protection and use of cultural heritage objects of the Ministry of Culture has reached an impasse due to the "thinning of adobe walls." According to the paradoxical thought of the head of the regional state inspectorate for the Republic of Karakalpakstan of the Department of the Ministry of Culture Kuanyshbek Sharipov, "to leave the monument in its original form meant to doom it to complete destruction over time" [2]. The head office of the Ministry of Culture of Uzbekistan denied the information about the demolition of the mausoleum, saying

that "the mausoleum was simply overlaid with a new building." The ministry also assured journalists that "it did not give permission for the remodel," but it is going to "form a commission that will travel around all the cities of our Homeland, inspect each monument and give its recommendations."

It seems that the restoration of the Institute is an urgent problem, but a simple decision of the government will not solve it. It is necessary to recreate the entire chain of training restorers and the organization of the restoration process. In order for competent specialists to reappear at the Institute of Restoration, they need to be educated at the university, and since there are no specialists of the proper level left at the architectural and construction Institute, it is necessary to find competent teachers capable of educating future restorers. To date, it has been confirmed that professionals clearly realized a quarter of a century ago: it is easy to destroy an institution, but it will take decades to restore it. However, in the Karimov years there was no one to resist the illiterate decisions of the president and his staff.

At the same time, it would be a mistake to think that the restoration of the destroyed institutions of the 1980s in itself would guarantee proper treatment of monuments. Unfortunately, the roots of the disease, which ended in death for the mausoleum of Shmunabi, lie much deeper. Journalists can, like Evgenia Grande, innocently throw rhetorical exclamations, such as "it's scary to think what else the hand of the absurd will touch – Registan, Arch, Toprak-Kale?". But architectural historians know for sure that this hand has long been stretched over the most famous monuments of Uzbekistan, including those named. And although well-known specialists were engaged in restoration in Uzbekistan in the last Soviet decades, the system itself, formed by the republican government, was already guided by ideological imperatives, which became dominant with the advent of Uzbekistan's independence.

The idea of Boris Zasytkin, one of the founders of the restoration business in Uzbekistan, was close to this principle back in the 1920s. "With all the documentarily of the parts being restored," "the restoration work aims not to affect

the preserved ancient parts by destruction or partial disassembly, but to do new completions in accordance with the ancient ones, but introducing signs and markings by which subsequent researchers could distinguish the authentic ancient parts from the restoration". The authors of the Venice Charter were only more radical, demanding that the reconstruction be carried out in the forms and materials of today's era, so that the differences between the original and the modern layer were obvious to everyone at first glance. However, by the 1970s, the restoration business in Uzbekistan had moved in a different direction. In particular, in the most famous Samarkand monuments – Registan, Bibi-Khanim, Gur-Emir and Shahi-Zinda – the new model gradually absorbed the original, and conservation successively gave way to restoration, and then almost complete reconstruction of the monument.

In the 19th century, madrasas amazed the imagination with huge brick masses towering over one-story streets and mahallas. Mosaic patterns, on the contrary, have not been preserved everywhere – much more on Shir-Dora, less on Ulugbek and Tillya-Kari madrasas. Today, arabesques cover almost the entire surface of the monuments. It is very difficult to distinguish the original fragments from modern ones, not because they are comparable in quality (just the opposite!), but primarily because the copy has almost completely absorbed the original. For example, photographs from the 19th century testified that the patterned majolica was preserved on an insignificant part of the tympanum of the Ulugbek madrasah and was not preserved at all on the portal of the Tillya-Kari madrasah. It could not have been otherwise: during the earthquake of 1821, the portal collapsed and subsequently, in the middle of the 19th century, it was roughly restored - the original decor on it could not be preserved. However, today it covers huge surfaces with a solid patterned carpet. And if in the case of the Ulugbek madrasah it can be assumed that the restored part reproduces the lost fragments in general terms, then as for Tillya-Kari, it is difficult to doubt the fantastical nature of Arabesques, most likely inspired by monuments of the same era. And this is not surprising: the patterns on medieval madrasahs were not applied according to pre-drawn drawings and such

drawings were not then handed over to the archive of the "Museum of Architecture" (even general information about the years of construction of Tillya-Kari was not preserved in the waqf records).

Moreover, no one could judge what its shape, height, drawing and materials were. Thus, what appeared above the drum of the mosque in the 1970s is a modern fantasy building inspired by the "average domes" of the 17th century. The official motive for its construction was the desire to protect the restored interior surfaces of the Tillya-Kari mosque from destruction and the effects of precipitation. However, with the help of modern materials, it was possible to erect a protective structure inside the drum, leaving the appearance of the madrasah intact. It seems that the fact is that in the restoration policy in Samarkand in the late Soviet decades, another trend gradually prevailed. The strengthening of structures and preservation of monuments, which were practiced in the 1920s and the museification of the entire complex, which peaked in the early 1960s, when Registan, having lost the mahalla adjacent to it, was built up by modernist Khrushchevs, was replaced by the desire to "recreate" the complex, serving the already formed desire of the republican authorities for visualization "the great past" of Uzbekistan.

Therefore, it seems to me that in goal setting it would be worth preferring internal civil tasks to external tourist ones. Architectural monuments, as well as all cultural heritage in general, are the property of society. Tourists will leave, but citizens will stay in the city, and it is in their interests not to live among fakes, impersonal spaces and orientalist spectacles. That is why the system of cultural heritage support needs to be reorganized as soon as possible. But to do this, citizens must be able to act as citizens, not subjects.

Literatures:

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